

IDENTIFYING RECENT CHANGES AND CHOOSING PERAK I SURABAYA'S CLIMATE PROJECTION

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Abstract

Proving climate change's existence and showing the best available projection in local area is difficult to be done. Data which are investigated come from Perak I Maritime Meteorological Station, Surabaya. Former study has been done using 1972-2012 data. Projection using RCP CSIRO-Mk3.6 RegCM4 is also done using base periode 1970-2005. Recently, Super El Nino happened in 2015. Re identification on climate change and evaluation climate models needs to be done for investigating the impact of the climatologic phenomenon. 29 indices from Rclimdex used as determination method for separating significant changing. Models are corrected and evaluated using data from 1972-2016 based RCP 4.5 and 8.5. Only 14 (13) from 29 indices show significant changing by base period 1972-2016 (1972-2012). Addition of last four years makes SDII significant although not caused neither by DJF nor JJA. DTR index of JJA 1972-2016 also be not significant. Indices show that temperature has changed either on its mean and distribution meanwhile precipitation generally shows no significant change. On the other side, 11 years evaluation shows similar rainfall (temperature) pattern with adjusted RCP 4.5 (8.5) scenario. Correction with real data is an absolute necessity while projection of rainfall (temperature) pattern in future shows declining (increasing) trend.

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1. Introduction

World Meteorological Organization (WMO) states that global temperature rising in 2016 is 0.88°C above 1961-1990 average temperatur. It is almost 1.2°C above pre-industrial era. Similar global temperature trends occur in Indonesia. The increasing of global temperature hipotehically has some impact on higher probability of heavy rain and distribution pattern of rainfall [1]. Climate change and global warming are so phenomenon and is clearly observed on a global scale [2]. Because of it, research is needed to find out the changes that are happening in smaller scale and its possible changes in the future.

Data used in this research are rainfall and temperature data observed from Maritime Station Perak I Surabaya with longitude 112.72°E and latitude 7.22°S. The station is located at provincial capital (second administrative level after central government in Indonesia) which is also an economic center of East Java. The data according to previous research [3] show that it experienced changes in temperature and not in precipitation patterns. Other studies before are in line with this finding [4-5]. Research from Supari [3] took temperature and precipitation data from same place, Surabaya from 1972 to 2012. On the other hand, this study uses data taken

from 1972 to 2016, or adding four years after the last one. In these four years, Super El Nino event was occurring and then famously named by 2015/2016 event [6]. This phenomenon's impact on climate change needs to be studied further.

After identifying recent changes, to estimate the possibility of further changes, BMKG (Indonesian meteorology climatology and geophysics agency) contributes to the South East Asia Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (SEA-Cordex). Projection (future prediction) is run based on 1970-2005 historical data. Until 2016, eleven years have gone so the projection evaluation can begin.

The first objective of this study was to determine changes in perspective of temperature and rainfall from observations at the station based on 1972-2016 data using some index. Then the second goal is to evaluate the results of projections and show the next possibilities that are more likely to occur in future. The result of this study is expected to be a reference to anticipate negative impact on environment and socio-politics sector caused by future climate change from global warming and local factors.

2.Data and Methods

Area around of study point is shown below in white circle. Red area shows residential area. So it can be said that the changes observed will impact human activities around.

Figure 1. Location of Perak I Surabaya

Data used in this study are daily minimum temperature, daily maximum temperature, and daily rainfall from Januari 1st 1972 till December 31st 2012 are obtained from BMKG Database Centre. Data is produced from synoptic observation in Maritim Station Perak I Surabaya. The rest four year data from January 1st 2013 till December 31st 2016 are downloaded Data Online BMKG link (<http://dataonline.bmkg.go.id>).

Obtained data is then be processed through quality control where missing data is replaced with -99.9, outlier data is removed, and so it will not disturb data's statistic profile. But not all outlier is removed. Some outlier related to special condition that can be justified by meteorological concept is included in next analysis. Baseline periode is determined to be 1981 till 2010, justified with normal periode that is used operationally by BMKG for making information about deviation [7]. This study compares identification changes based on 1972-2012 (41 years) data with newer periode 1972-2016 (45 years). Seasonal grouping before

indexing is also done using DJF (December January February) which is representing wet periode and JJA (Juny July August) for dry one.

Software from Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices (ETCDDI) called CLIMDEX or Rclimdex is used. This software is also used in many studies [1, 8-9]. 29 index used are as follows [10]: FD (number of frost days; temperature; $T < 0^{\circ}\text{C}$), SU (number of summer days; T maximum; $\text{TX} > 25^{\circ}\text{C}$), ID (number of icing days; T minimum; $\text{TN} < 0^{\circ}\text{C}$), TR (number of tropical night; $\text{TN} > 20^{\circ}\text{C}$), GSL (growing season length), TXx (monthly maximum value of daily maximum temperature), TNx (monthly maximum value of daily minimum temperature), TXn (monthly minimum value of daily maximum temperature), TNn (monthly minimum value of daily minimum temperature), TN10p (percentage of days when $\text{TN} < 10\text{th}$ percentile; all percentil value based on 1981-2010 period), TX10p (percentage of days when $\text{TX} < 10\text{th}$ percentile), TN90p (percentage of days when $\text{TN} > 90\text{th}$ percentile), TX90p (percentage of days when $\text{TX} > 90\text{th}$ percentile), WSDI, (warm spell duration index; annual count of days with at least 6 consecutive days when $\text{TX} > 90\text{th}$ percentile), CSDI (cold spell duration index; annual count of days with at least 6 consecutive days when $\text{TN} < 10\text{th}$ percentile), DTR (Daily temperature range: Monthly mean difference between TX and TN), Rx1day (monthly maximum 1-day precipitation), Rx5day (monthly maximum consecutive 5-day precipitation), SDII (simple pricipitation intensity index), R10mm (annual count of days when $\text{PRCP} \geq 10\text{mm}$), R20mm (annual count of days when $\text{PRCP} \geq 20\text{mm}$), R50mm (annual count of days when $\text{PRCP} \geq 50\text{mm}$), CDD (maximum length of dry spell, maximum number of consecutive days with $\text{RR} < 1\text{mm}$), CWD (maximum length of wet spell, maximum number of consecutive days with $\text{RR} \geq 1\text{mm}$), R95pTOT (annual total PRCP when $\text{RR} > 95\text{th}$ percentile), R99pTOT (annual total PRCP when $\text{RR} > 99\text{th}$ percentile), PRCPTOT (annual total precipitation in wet days), TXmean (mean of maksimum temperature), and TNmean (mean of minimum temperature).

The projection model eavaluated in this study is run by BMKG Center for Research and Development using two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), 4.5 and 8.5. RCP 8.5 manifest worst condition that is identical to A2R SRES [11] while RCP 4.5 is assumed to occur in more realistic adaptive and mitigative policies with a constant population after 2050 [12]. Global climate model (GCM) used is CSIRO MK3.6 [13-14]. Regional climate model (RCM) used is RegCM4 [15, Elguindi, et al., 2011].

Data extraction is carried out using R Statistics. Moreover, corrections are made on a monthly scale using following correction formula [16]. Reference period is same as normal period used.

$$\text{Rainfall}_{\text{corrected}} = \{ \text{Rainfall}_{\text{obs ref}} / \text{Rainfall}_{\text{model ref}} \} * \text{Rainfall}_{\text{model}} \quad (2.1)$$

$$\text{Temperature}_{\text{corrected}} = \{ \text{Temperature}_{\text{obs ref}} - \text{Temperature}_{\text{model ref}} \} + \text{Temperature}_{\text{model}} \quad (2.2)$$

Mean Absolute Error (MAE) used as comparison parameter to determine best projection is formulated as below [17].

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum (|X_{\text{model}} - X_{\text{obs}}|) \quad (2.3)$$

Some definitions are used to simplify division of time range in this study as follows: reference (1972-2005), base (1972-2016), near (2017-2039), mid (2040- 2069), and far (2070-2099). These definitions are an approach of the 30-year normal concept.

Result and Discussion

Figure 2. Significant 1972-2016 indices identification

Results of using 29 Rclimdex indices are then categorized as in figure 2. Significant or not classification is carried out using p-value and comparing slope with slope error. Significant changes will only be justified if the p-value is less than 0.05 and slope estimate is greater than slope error. This concept has been explained by Sensoy before [18]. At least 5 indices are identified as not suitable to be used in tropical region. Using data from the period 1972-2016 (1972-2012), there are 14 (13) indices that are significant. The indices are DTR, CSDI, WSDI, TN90P, TN10P, TX90P, TX10P, TNn, TNx, TXn, TXx, TXmean, TNmean, and SDII.

Figure 3. WSDI (left) and DTR (right) graph period 1972-2016

WSDI (CSDI) graph only shows increasing (decreasing) pattern on the right (left) side as shown in figure 3. Significant WSDI (CSDI) show that temperature which is relatively hot (cold) in a row will occur (not occur) more frequent in the future. Other graphs are more variative which mean there is no one side only of either increasing or decreasing. Increasing pattern of the DTR (figure 3) shows that the difference between maximum and minimum temperatures in the future will be wider. On the other hand, there are only three indices that show significant decreasing trend. One of them is CSDI and the other two temperature indices with 10th percentile-based indices. Supporting it, temperature 90th percentile-based indices are significant too. It means that the distribution will be wider so hotter and colder happen simultaneously.

Figure 4. SDII 1972-2012 (left) and 1972-2016 (right)

The interesting point is that there is only one (none) index related to precipitation shows significant changes in the period 1972-2016 (1972-2012). 4 years data (2013-2016) make SDII be significant. SDII using 1972-2012 data has p-value of 0.422 and becomes 0.047 after the extension (figure 4). Decreased p-value only after added four year data indicates that Super El Nino can create bias. It makes further climate change plot should be more aware about choosing or splitting time border near Super El Nino event. However, the results of this study still confirm what Supari [3] has said that there are very few rainfall indices whose significant trends. In fact, there were only two precipitation indices with slope error values smaller than its slope estimate. Its p-value are 0.31 (R20mm) and 0.074 (CDD).

Trends in temperature percentile-based indices have average about 0.361 per year or equivalent to 10.83 in just 30 years. Moreover on 1972-2016 TX90P index, the value reached 0.681 per year (20.43°C hotter in just 30 years). This shows that the increasing in temperature is not only caused by some data, but its distribution is changed. Trend per year shows 0.05 for maximum temperature and 0.03 for the minimum. With business as usual, warming be around 3°C-5°C.

Figure 5. Schematic temperature shifting in Perak I: recent (solid) and future (dots)

Only four indices (DTR, SDII, TXmean, dan TNmean) that can be used for DJF and JJA data. SDII be still not significant using this grouping. It means the changes shown by SDII are

generated by outside DJF and JJA period which the rainfall prediction is relatively harder due to monsoonal transition. From temperature indices, there is no significant difference between using either all time data and grouped data or 41 years and 45 years data.

Figure 6. Correction factor for temperature (in celcius) and rainfall (in percent)

After identifying the changes, model evaluation is carried out after examining some correction factor. Figure 6 shows the variation of correction factor for monthly temperature and rainfall. It can be seen that correction factor of monthly rainfall from comparing it with observation data is quite varied. The most different factor is in September maybe due to monsoon which makes the month be some transitional condition between dry to wet. The factor above can be used for correction by multiplying it after plus one. For temperature, correction be as simple as adding the value to model's value from 2006 - 2099. Otherwise, it is also shown that maximum temperature of the model is more similar than the minimum one except for November and December. Maximum temperature from model tends to be lower than observation, especially from July to December. For minimum temperature, it is constantly higher than observation.

Figure 7. Temperature (left) and rainfall (right) model evaluation for 2006-2016 periods

Comparing temperature models by displaying to some point (28oC) is done due to simplify maximum and minimum temperature to be range. MAE values for both graphics are shown in parentheses (" "). For temperature model, corrected (crr) RCP 8.5 shows the narrowest difference with observations and also smallest MAE. It means that RCP 8.5 shows best projection for temperature. On the other hand, corrected RCP 4.5 is the best for rainfall. From this fact, it can be stated that correction processes make significant different. Group of

uncorrected models also always have higher MAE. Because of there is no single better RCP for

temperature and rainfall, all corrected projections are shown.

Figure 8. Temperature (left) and rainfall (right) projections

Warmer condition is coming. Graph above shows that intensive warming is projected to occur in the 2040s. Even if RCP 4.5 scenario can be achieved, maximum temperature increase will still reach the 35-35°C and minimum temperatures follow at 25-26°C. More studies about the impact of this warming on a worst level are better to do, because the temperatures tend to lead to RCP 8.5's. Although corrected RCP 4.5 pattern proved to be superior compared to RCP 8.5 in 2006-2016, monthly rainfall from model outputs show no significant different. Both RCPs show monthly rainfall decline. It implies that water resources management planning needs to be more advanced. Moreover in RCP 4.5, the decline actually little bit sharper in the near (2017-2039) period than mid (2040-2069).

Conclusion

Three meteorological parameters (rainfall, maximum temperature, and minimum temperature) from Maritime Station Perak I Surabaya has been analyzed. From 29 climate change indices that have been reviewed there are only less than half of the significant indices. Only SDII, one of rainfall index, that becomes significant after adding four years (2013-2016). Changes in temperature is very clear so that the average will be higher consistently with distribution shifting to warmer condition but there is no significant changes in rainfall pattern. It is also shown that further study should avoid or at least give some higher attention in choosing time border near Super El Nino event. Using seasonal framework will give no different result. This study also shows that correction using observation data for projection model output is a must. To simplify the graph, maximum and minimum temperature can be converted as difference temperature related to some fixed point. Warmer and drier condition is expected to be happen in the future.

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